

SADT MODELING OF A CULTURAL PROJECT

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Abstract

Purpose – Cultural products of any kind must be the result of a logical and methodical managerial process with objectives, activities, resources, and especially indicators that are properly defined and accomplished according to the forecasts.

Without altering the artistic component, which is creative and defining for the cultural product, the scientific management, based on rules, procedures, models and working algorithms developed in the last century, especially in the business sphere, also develops in areas that do not necessarily follow additional gain but it ensures efficiency corresponding to artistic work.

Methodology/approach - The methodology used involves identifying the main activities of the process of creating and implementing a theatrical performance and defining the parameters in which these steps will be managed - inputs, outputs, conditions, rules and prescriptions, existing or acquired resources, etc.

The SADT model designed to theatre performances will have a character of universality and will be tailored to each situation.

Findings – The SADT model seeks to professionalize the management of the performance staging process so that the proposed objectives and pre-established indicators are respected and even improved.

The created model does not generate understanding problems or additional skills for managers in the cultural sector but ensures the correct implementation of the management act.

Research limitations/implications – Having experience in the management of theater performance, the authors of the paper found a series of inadequacies in the managerial act leading to waste of resources and of course not respecting the objectives initially assumed (quality, duration of implementation, additional costs, scattered human energy, etc.).

Practical implications – The contribution of the paper is that it transfers from the scientific management a method of systemic modeling in a sector, the cultural one, which needs managerial efficiency and efficiency.

Originality/value – This paper, for the first time in Romania, transfers one of the SADT system simulation methods already widely used in project management, developed in the US but widely used in all countries and fields of activity.

Key words: SADT, cultural project, managerial performance

1. The advantages of applying the SADT method in cultural productions

The present paper presents the usefulness of prioritizing the functions of a cultural production based on the SADT method defined by Douglas T. Ross and known among specialists (Hunt D., Process Mapping. How to Reengineer your Business Process, Ed. J. Wiley, N.Y., 1996, Marca D., Structured Analysis and Design Technique, McGraw-Hill, London, 2006, Mylopoulos J., SADT Diagrams, www.cs.toronto.edu, 2004) in systems analysis as the IDEFO method. It brings a number of advantages that managers of cultural institutions can not ignore:

- represents a synthetic, realistic and correctly argued decision support;

- presents in stages, from the beginning to the end, the activities that contribute to the materialization of a cultural product;
- explains the specific processes of the system and creates the possibility of analysing each component of the activities without which it cannot fulfil its specific objective;
- processes are fully defined only if their components are nominated: inputs, outputs, information and control rules and, last but not least, the resources needed for the specific transformations of each process;
- the flow chart of cultural production made by an initiated and experienced system analyst is a synthetic document that can be used by the manager to streamline activities by framing processes in the initial prescriptions (resources, specific conditions, stage objectives, specific performances, etc.). ;
- diagrams are dialogue tools, they can be commented, annotated or completed by all those interested in achieving superior performance (cost reductions, elimination of unnecessary activities, etc.);
- the created tool can be used in process monitoring, and by adding a Gantt chart it can be used in managing the implementation of the process itself;
- for certain cultural productions with common characteristics (theatre performances, exhibitions, conferences, etc.), preconceptualized SADT schemes can be used. They will adapt to each particular situation, thus facilitating the process of analysis and design of the flow chart. Analysts and managers thus use contingent solutions in which experience and the ability to identify the particularities of each cultural production greatly reduce intellectual effort and working time.

2. Notions about SADT modelling specific to the realization of a theatrical performance.

The basis of the SADT model is the cultural function, in our case a complex of activities that ultimately leads to the achievement of a clearly defined objective. It is a product materialized in a theatrical performance, which in turn can be derived, due to partial objectives specific to each significant activity, for the materialization of the cultural act.

This activity, the core for the SADT method (Marian L., Project management, Ed. Efi-Rom, Tg.Mureş, 2001), represented by a rectangle, is defined by the action that it performs. It has specific input sizes, in fact the elements that will be processed in the module (the input arrows left side), has the resources with which the activity will be performed (the arrows at the bottom of the module), information on working technique and control methods (arrows at the top of the module) and the product / service achieved by the specific transformation of the module (the output arrows right side). In the nomination of the modules two actigram methods are used: the method that uses the defining verb for the module and the other one naming the product created as datagram. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. SADT module structure

A complex function can be decomposed into several component subfunctions that can in turn have subcomponents, and the more detailed the decomposition, the more comprehensive the SADT analysis

becomes and the more successfully it can be used in the cultural product management. Rarely are cultural products that can be created through a single action and with little diversified resources. Most of them are created through multiple activities that are each represented by functional blocks logically chained forming a flow chart which highlights the sequential development of the complex process. Figure 2 shows the flow chart of the processes specific to the staging of a theatre play, the first SADT scheme made in Romania for cultural productions.

Figure 2. Flowchart of the staging of a play

Based on a systemic analysis of the processes that are carried out in the staging of a theatre play, 7 basic modules were defined which are then in turn expanded into submodules with specific activities and derived activities from each basic module.

A. The Choice of the theatre play

- A1. The minimum annual program
- A2. Use of human resources (actors, directors, set designers, etc.)
- A3. Sources of funding
- A4. Performance Opening Nights planning
- A5. Collaborators

B. Ensuring working conditions

- B1. Casting
- B2. Sets sketches
- B3. Costumes Sketches
- B4. Elaboration of the Technical Conditions Sheet

B5. Production estimate

B6. Copyrights

C. The actor's art

C1. Objectives, messages, purposes

C2. Individual rehearsals

C3. Collective rehearsals

C4. General rehearsals

D. The environment

D1. Sets

D2. Costumes

D3. Technical conditions (sound, lights, special effects, etc.)

E. Management

E1. Supply

E2. Financial management

E3. Promotion

F. Launch of the cultural product

F1. Technical rehearsal

F2. General rehearsal

F3. Opening Night

G. Product operation

G1. Performances planning

G2. Transport

G3. Technical maintenance

G4. Performance marketing

To the graphical representation of Figure 2 there is attached a synoptic document in the form of a table – Table 1. - which contains all the components and characteristics of the modules necessary for their definition according to the SADT methodology.

Table1. Synoptic table of SADT module components

Module	Name	Inputs	Resources / Facilities	Information / Control	Output	Notes

The basic modules can in turn be represented in a cascade of sub-activities performed sequentially using the aforementioned work technique. For example, module C The actor's art has as inputs the outputs from the previous module B: technical conditions, casting, director and adapted text, and the output is the mastering of roles, activities that are expanded and represented by the flow chart in Figure.3

Figure 3. Flowchart of C module

Conclusions

The SADT method used for the first time in Romania when staging a theatrical performance proves to be a useful and necessary procedure. It highlights the stages, means, conditions and conditionalities that must be observed in order to obtain efficiency and managerial efficiency. The conditions for using this procedure are minimal: availability for systemic analysis of procedures, relatively average knowledge of the SADT technique and the desire to manage through a proper management performances as attractive as possible to viewers.

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